

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 104

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 104

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 104:1 "Bless the LORD, O my soul! O LORD my God, You are very great; You are ^bclothed with splendor and majesty, ² Covering Yourself with ^alight as with a cloak, ^bStretching out heaven like a <i>tent</i> curtain. ³ ¹He ^alays the beams of His upper chambers in the waters; ¹He makes the ^bclouds His chariot; ¹He walks upon the ^cwings of the wind; ⁴ ¹He makes ^{2a}the winds His messengers, ³Flaming ^bfire His ministers.</p> <p>Psa. 104:5 He ^aestablished the earth upon its foundations, So that it will not ¹totter forever and ever. ⁶ You ^acovered it with the deep as with a garment; The waters were standing above the mountains. ⁷ At Your ^arebuke they fled, At the ^bsound of Your thunder they hurried away. ⁸ The mountains rose; the valleys sank down To the ^aplace which You established for them.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 104:1 בְּרַכֵּי נַפְשִׁי אֶת־יְהוָה יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי גִבְרַת פֶּאֶד הַיּוֹד וְהַדָּר לְבָשֶׁת : ² עֲטֶה אֹר כַּשְּׂלֵמָה נוֹטָה שָׁמַיִם פִּירִיעָה : ³ הַמְקַרָּה בַּמַּיִם עַל־יֹתֵיב הַשָּׁמַיִם עֲבִים רְכוּבוֹ הַמְהַלֵּךְ עַל־כַּנְפֵי־רוּחַ : ⁴ עֲשֶׂה מִלְאֲכָיו רוּחוֹת מְשָׁרְתָיו אֵשׁ לֵהִט : ⁵ יִסַּד אֶרֶץ עַל־מְכוּנֶיהָ בַּל־תִּפְּוֹשׁ עוֹלָם וָעֶד : ⁶ תִּהְיוּ כַּלְבוּשׁ כַּסִּיתוֹ עַל־הָרִים יַעֲמֵדוּ־ מַיִם : ⁷ מִן־גְּעַרְתָּךְ יִנוּסוּן מִן־קוֹל רַעֲמֶךָ יִחַפְּזוּן : ⁸ יַעֲלוּ הָרִים יִרְדּוּ בְּקַעֲוֹת אֶל־מְקוֹם זֶה אִיסְדָּתָ לָהֶם : ⁹ גִּבּוֹל־שָׁמַיִת בַּל־יַעֲבְרוּן בַּל־יִשׁוּבוּן לְכַסּוֹת הָאָרֶץ : ¹⁰ הַמְשַׁלַּח מֵעַנְיָנִים בְּנִחְלִים בֵּין הָרִים יִהְלְכוּן : ¹¹ יִשְׁקוּ כָּל־חַיֵּיתוֹ שָׂרֵי יִשְׁבְּרוּ פְּרָאִים צְמָאִם : ¹² עַל־יָהֶם עוֹף־הַשָּׁמַיִם יִשְׁכּוּן מִבֵּין עֲפָאִים יִתְנוּ־קוֹל : ¹³ מִשְׁקָה הָרִים מֵעַל־יֹתֵיב מִפְּרֵי מַעֲשֵׂיךָ תִּשְׁבַּע הָאָרֶץ : ¹⁴ מִצְמִיחַ תְּצִיר אֶל־בְּהֵמָה וְעֹשֵׁב לַעֲבֹדֵת הָאָדָם לְהוֹצִיא לָהֶם מִן־הָאָרֶץ : ¹⁵ וַיֵּן אִישְׁמַח</p>

⁹ You set a ^aboundary that they may not pass over,
So that they will not return to cover the earth.

Psa. 104:10 ¹He sends forth ^asprings in the valleys;

They flow between the mountains;

¹¹ They ^agive drink to every beast of the field;

The ^bwild donkeys quench their thirst.

¹² ¹Beside them the birds of the heavens ^a dwell;

They ²lift up *their* voices among the branches.

¹³ ¹He ^awaters the mountains from His upper chambers;

^bThe earth is satisfied with the fruit of His works.

Psa. 104:14 ¹He causes the ^agrass to grow for the ²cattle,

And ^bvegetation for the ³labor of man,

So that ⁴he may bring forth ⁵food ^afrom the earth,

¹⁵ And ^awine which makes man's heart glad,

^bSo that he may make *his* face glisten with oil,

And ¹food which ^csustains man's heart.

¹⁶ The trees of the LORD ¹drink their fill,

The cedars of Lebanon which He planted,

¹⁷ Where the ^abirds build their nests,

And the ^bstork, whose home is the ¹fir trees.

לְבַב-אֲנוּשׁ לְהַצְהִיל פְּנִים מִשָּׁמַן

וְלָחֶם לְבַב-אֲנוּשׁ יִסְעֶד : ¹⁶ יִשְׁבְּעוּ

עֲצֵי יְהוָה אֲרָזֵי לְבָנוֹן אֲשֶׁר נִטְעוּ :

¹⁷ אֲשֶׁר-שָׁם צִפְּרִים יִקְנְנוּ חֲסִידָה

בְּרוּשִׁים בֵּיתָה : ¹⁸ הַרְרִים הַגְּבֹהִים

לִיַּעֲלִים סְלָעִים מִחֶסֶה לְשִׁפְּנִים : ¹⁹

עָשָׂה יָרַח לְמוֹעֲדִים שָׁמֵשׁ יָרַע

מִבּוֹאוֹ : ²⁰ תָּשֶׁת-חֶשֶׁךְ וַיְהִי לַיְלָה

בּוֹ-תִרְמָשׁ כָּל-חַיְתוֹ-יַעַר : ²¹

הַכְּפִירִים שֹׁאֲגִים לַטָּרֶף וּלְבִקֵּשׁ

מֵאֵל אֲכָלִים : ²² תִּזְרַח הַשָּׁמֶשׁ

וְאִסְפוּן וְאֵל-מְעוֹנֹתָם יִרְבְּצוּן : ²³

יֵצֵא אָרְם לְפַעֲלוֹ וְלַעֲבֹדָתוֹ עֲרֵי-

עָרָב : ²⁴ מָה-רָבוּ מֵעֵשִׂיף וַיְהוּה

כָּלֶם בְּחִכְמָה עָשִׂיתָ מְלֵאָה הָאָרֶץ

קִנְיִנָּךְ : ²⁵ זֶה אֵתִים גְּדוֹל וְרָחֵב

יָדַיִם שָׁם-רָמַשׁ וְאֵין מִסְפָּר חַיּוֹת

קְטַנּוֹת עַם-גְּדֹלוֹת : ²⁶ שָׁם אֲנִיּוֹת

יִהְלְכוּן לְוִיָּתָן זֶה-יִצְרֹף לְשִׁחִק-

בּוֹ : ²⁷ כָּלֶם אֲלֵיךָ יִשְׁבְּרוּן לְתַת

אֲכָלִים בְּעֵתוֹ : ²⁸ תִּתֵּן לָהֶם יִלְקַטוּן

תִּפְתַּח יָרֵךְ יִשְׁבְּעוּן טוֹב : ²⁹ תִּסְתִּיר

פְּנֵיךָ יִבְהַלּוּן תִּסְרֶה רֵוְחָם יִגֹּעוּן

וְאֵל-עִפְרָם יִשׁוּבוּן : ³⁰ תִּשְׁלַח

רוּחְךָ יִבְרָאוּן וְתַתִּיֵּשׁ פְּנֵי אֲדָמָה :

³¹ יְהִי כְבוֹד יְהוָה לְעוֹלָם יִשְׁמַח

יְהוָה בְּמַעֲשָׂיו : ³² תִּמְבִּיט לְאָרֶץ

וְתִרְעַד יַגַּע בְּהַרְרִים וַיַּעֲשֵׂנוּ : ³³

Psa. 104:18 The high mountains are for the "wild goats;

The ^bcliffs are a refuge for the ^{1c}shephanim.

¹⁹ He made the moon ^afor the seasons;

The ^bsun knows the place of its setting.

²⁰ You ^aappoint darkness and it becomes night,

In which all the ^bbeasts of the forest ¹prowl about.

²¹ The ^ayoung lions roar after their prey

¹And ^bseek their food from God.

²² *When* the sun rises they withdraw
And lie down in their ^adens.

²³ Man goes forth to ^ahis work
And to his labor until evening.

Psa. 104:24 O LORD, how ^amany are Your works!

¹In ^bwisdom You have made them all;

The 'earth is full of Your ²possessions.

²⁵ ¹There is the ^asea, great and ²broad,
In which are swarms without number,

Animals both small and great.

²⁶ There the ^aships move along,
And ^{1b}Leviathan, which You have formed to sport in it.

Psa. 104:27 They all ^await for You

To ^bgive them their food in ¹due season.

²⁸ You give to them, they gather *it* up;
You ^aopen Your hand, they are satisfied with good.

אֲשִׁירָה לַיהוָה בְּתֵיבֵי אֲזִמְרָה
לְאֱלֹהֵי בְּעֹזִי: ³⁴ יַעֲרֹב עָלָיו שִׁיחֵי
אֲנָכִי אֲשַׁמַּח בִּיהוָה: ³⁵ יִתְמַו
חַטָּאִים אֶמֶן-הָאָרֶץ וּרְשָׁעִים אַעֲוֹד
אֵינָם בְּרַכִּי נִפְשֵׁי אֶת-יְהוָה הַלְלוּ-
יְהוָה:

²⁹ You ^ahide Your face, they are dismayed;

You ^btake away their ¹spirit, they expire

And ^creturn to their dust.

³⁰ You send forth Your ^{1a}Spirit, they are created;

And You renew the face of the ground.

Psa. 104:31 Let the ^aglory of the LORD endure forever;

Let the LORD ^bbe glad in His works;

³² ¹He ^alooks at the earth, and it ^btrembles;

He ^ctouches the mountains, and they smoke.

³³ ¹I will sing to the LORD ^{2a}as long as I live;

¹I will ^bsing praise to my God ³while I have my being.

³⁴ Let my ^ameditation be pleasing to Him;

As for me, I shall ^bbe glad in the LORD.

³⁵ Let sinners be ^aconsumed from the earth

And let the ^bwicked be no more.

^aBless the LORD, O my soul.

^{1a}Praise ²the LORD!

References

Psalm 104:1

^aPs 103:22

^bPs 93:1

Psalm 104:2

^aDan 7:9

^bIs 40:22

Psalm 104:3

¹Lit *The one who*

^aAmos 9:6

^bIs 19:1

Ps 18:10

Psalm 104:4

¹Lit *Who*

²Or *His angels, spirits*

³Or *His ministers flames of fire*

^aPs 148:8; Heb 1:7

^b2 Kin 2:11; 6:17

Psalm 104:5

¹Or *move out of place*

^aJob 38:4; Ps 24:2

Psalm 104:6

^aGen 1:2

Psalm 104:7

^aPs 18:15; 106:9; Is 50:2

^bPs 29:3; 77:18

Psalm 104:8

^aPs 33:7

Psalm 104:9

^aJob 38:10, 11; Jer 5:22

Psalm 104:10

¹Lit *The one who sends*
^aPs 107:35; Is 41:18

Psalm 104:11

^aPs 104:13
^bJob 39:5

Psalm 104:12

¹Or *Over, Above*
²Lit *give forth*
^aMatt 8:20

Psalm 104:13

¹Lit *Who*
^aPs 65:9; 147:8
^bJer 10:13

Psalm 104:14

¹Lit *Who*
²Or *beasts*
³Or *cultivation by or service of*
⁴Or *He*
⁵Lit *bread*
^aJob 38:27; Ps 147:8
^bGen 1:29
^cJob 28:5

Psalm 104:15

¹Lit *bread*
^aJudg 9:13; Prov 31:6; Eccl 10:19
^bPs 23:5; 92:10; 141:5; Luke 7:46
^cGen 18:5; Judg 19:5, 8

Psalm 104:16

¹Lit *are satisfied*

Psalm 104:17

¹Or *cypress*
^aPs 104:12
^bLev 11:19

Psalm 104:18

¹Small, shy, furry animals (*Hyrax syriacus*) found in the peninsula of the Sinai, northern Israel, and the region round the Dead Sea; KJV *coney*, orig NASB *rock badgers*

^aJob 39:1

^bProv 30:26

^cLev 11:5

Psalm 104:19

^aGen 1:14

^bPs 19:6

Psalm 104:20

¹Lit *creep*

^aPs 74:16; Is 45:7

^bPs 50:10; Is 56:9; Mic 5:8

Psalm 104:21

¹Lit *And to seek*

^aJob 38:39

^bPs 145:15; Joel 1:20

Psalm 104:22

^aJob 37:8

Psalm 104:23

^aGen 3:19

Psalm 104:24

¹Or *With*

²Or *creatures*

^aPs 40:5

^bPs 136:5; Prov 3:19; Jer 10:12; 51:15

^cPs 65:9

Psalm 104:25

¹Or *This*

²Or *broad of dimensions* (lit *hands*)

^aPs 8:8; 69:34

Psalm 104:26

¹Or *a sea monster*

^aPs 107:23; Ezek 27:9
^bJob 41:1; Ps 74:14; Is 27:1

Psalm 104:27

¹Lit *its appointed time*

^aPs 145:15

^bJob 36:31; 38:41; Ps 136:25; 147:9

Psalm 104:28

^aPs 145:16

Psalm 104:29

¹Or *breath*

^aDeut 31:17; Ps 30:7

^bJob 34:14, 15; Ps 146:4; Eccl 12:7

^cGen 3:19; Job 10:9; Ps 90:3

Psalm 104:30

¹Or *breath*

^aJob 33:4; Ezek 37:9

Psalm 104:31

^aPs 86:12; 111:10

^bGen 1:31

Psalm 104:32

¹Lit *The one who*

^aJudg 5:5; Ps 97:4, 5; 114:7

^bHab 3:10

^cEx 19:18; Ps 144:5

Psalm 104:33

¹Or *Let me sing*

²Lit *in my lifetime*

³Lit *while I still am*

^aPs 63:4

^bPs 146:2

Psalm 104:34

^aPs 19:14

^bPs 9:2

Psalm 104:35

¹Or *Hallelujah!*

²Heb *YAH*

^aPs 59:13

^bPs 37:10

^cPs 104:1

^dPs 105:45; 106:48

Targum

Psa. 104:1 Bless, O my soul, the name of the LORD. O LORD my God, you are greatly exalted; you have put on praise and splendor. ² Who wraps himself in light like a sheet, who stretches out the heavens like a curtain. ³ Who covers his chambers with water like a building with beams; who placed his chariot, as it were, upon swift clouds; who goes on the wings of an eagle. ⁴ Who made his messengers as swift as wind; his servants, as strong as burning fire. ⁵ Who lays the foundation of the earth upon its base, so that it will not shake for ages upon ages. ⁶ You have covered over the abyss as with a garment; and the waters split on the mountains, and endure. ⁷ At your rebuke, they will flee, flowing down; at the sound of your shout, they will be frightened, pouring themselves out. ⁸ They will go up from the abyss to the mountains, and descend to the valleys, to this place that you founded for them. ⁹ You have placed a boundary for the waves of the sea that they will not cross, lest they return to cover the earth. ¹⁰ Who releases springs into rivers; they flow between the mountains. ¹¹ They water all the wild animals; the asses will break their thirst. ¹² The birds of heaven will settle on them; they will give out a sound of singing from among the branches. ¹³ Who waters the mountains from his upper treasury; the earth will be satisfied with the fruit of your deeds. ¹⁴ Who makes grass grow for beasts, and herbs for the cultivation of the son of man, that bread may come forth from the earth; ¹⁵ And wine that gladdens the heart of the son of man, to make the face shine by oil; and bread will support the heart of the son of man. ¹⁶ The trees that the LORD created are satisfied, the cedars of Lebanon that he planted: ¹⁷ Where the birds make nests; the stork's dwelling is in the cypresses. ¹⁸ The high mountains are for the wild goats; the rocks are security for the conies. ¹⁹ He made the moon to calculate times by; the sun knows the time of his setting. ²⁰ You will make darkness and it will be night; in it all the beasts of the forest creep about. ²¹ The offspring of lions roar to find food, and to seek their sustenance from God. ²² The sun will shine, they gather together; and they lay down in their dwelling place. ²³ A son of man will go forth to his work and to his cultivation, until the sunset of evening. ²⁴ How many are your works, O LORD! You have made all of them in wisdom; the earth is full of your possessions. ²⁵ This sea is great and broad in extent; creeping things are there without number, both tiny creatures and large. ²⁶ There the ships go about, [and] this Leviathan you created for the sport of the righteous at the supper of his dwelling place. ²⁷ All of them rely on you to give their food in its time. ²⁸ You will give it to them, and they gather it; you will open your hand, and they are satisfied with goodness. ²⁹ You will remove your presence, they are dazed; you will gather their spirit and they expire, and return to their dust. ³⁰ You will send out your holy spirit and they are created; and you will make new the surface of the earth. ³¹ May the glory of the LORD be eternal; the LORD will rejoice in his works. ³² Who looks at the earth, and it shakes; he draws near to the mountains, and they emit smoke. ³³ I will sing praise in the presence of the LORD during my life; I will make music to my God while I exist. ³⁴ May my talk be pleasing in

his presence; I will rejoice in the word of the LORD. ³⁵ The sinners will be destroyed from the earth, and wicked exist no longer. Bless, O my soul, the name of the LORD. Hallelujah!

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm is a continuation of the preceding one. David recounts the greatness of the six days of Creation. He speaks about the splendor of the Light of Ein Sof, which created the Sefirot, Heaven, and Earth. The crowning glory of Creation was the creation of humankind. This Psalm is sung on Rosh Chodesh, the first day of the new month.

Notes of this Psalm

In David's day, nothing was taken for granted. He gave thanksgiving to the LORD in several Psalms for all the wonders of Creation. People today tend to take the LORD for granted. Ask yourself, when was the last time you gave thanksgiving to the LORD for the simple things that are usually taken for granted. A pastor offered a thanksgiving prayer before dinner and thanked the LORD for all the components of the dinner, not just the food. He gave thanks for the knives, forks, table, and more. Understanding that everything is a product of the LORD's six days of Creation will make a person humble and grateful before the LORD.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

